

iAtlantic

INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT OF ATLANTIC
MARINE ECOSYSTEMS IN SPACE AND TIME

Deliverable 7.1

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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1. iAtlantic Data Management Plan (DMP)

1.1 History of changes

History of changes Version	Date	Change	Authors
1.0	03.09.2019	Draft	Tina Dohna (UniHB)
2.0	20.05.2022	Contact person UniHB Trusted data repositories Data policy contents	Tina Dohna (UniHB) Malik Naumann (UniHB)

1.2 H2020's Open Research Data Pilot

The Commission is running a flexible pilot under Horizon 2020 called the **Open Research Data Pilot** (ORD pilot) that the iAtlantic project is participating in. The pilot addresses the challenging task of implementing wider access to research data and information for researchers, encouraging and enabling the re-use of data generated with H2020 funding, and to build trust in research results through open access data publications. The ORD is now applicable by default for all thematic areas of H2020 and its legal requirements are contained in the Article 29 of the iAtlantic Grant Agreement. All iAtlantic project partners must comply with **Article 29 of the Grant Agreement**. In line with the ORD, this iAtlantic Data Management Plan (DMP) specifies what data the research will generate, describes its curation, preservation and sustainability, and describes how the data will be openly made available. The ORD Pilot is a sensible and very timely investment on part of the European Commission and iAtlantic will actively support it by implementing innovative and effective open science practices among the international consortium of the project.

There is also an increasing awareness and willingness of the scientific community to move towards the FAIR data approach to make data not just open access but Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, since 2017 recommended by the Association of European Research Libraries.¹

1.3 H2020's Data Management Plan (DMP)

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy with regard to all data sets that will be generated by the project. The DMP is not a fixed document, but evolves during the lifespan of the project. The DMP should address the points below on a data set by data set basis and should record the current status of reflection within the consortium about the data that will be produced (source: European Commission DGRI. 2016. Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020).

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FAIR_data

- **Data set reference and name** - Identifier for the data set to be produced.
- **Data set description** - Description of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin (in case it is collected), nature and scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse.
- **Standards and metadata** - Reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created.
- **Data sharing** - Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In cases where the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).
- **Archiving and preservation** (including storage and backup) - Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

The DMP also records and provides 'opt-out' justifications for data that cannot be made openly available due to reasons of privacy, intellectual property rights, or in the case that open access may jeopardise the project's main objectives.

1.4 iAtlantic Grant Agreement - Article 29

Dissemination of results, open access and visibility of EU funding

The Data Management Plan and Open Science Policy of the iAtlantic project address Article 29 of the Grant agreement (after H2020 Programme, AGA –Annotated Model Grant Agreement²). It is included here as a key reference:

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

29.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 30 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1) — need to formally notify the Agency before dissemination takes place.

29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; **Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.**
- b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - i. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - ii. within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:
 - i. the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;

- ii. the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- iii. the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- iv. a persistent identifier.

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:

- a)** Deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - i. the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
 - ii. not applicable;
 - iii. other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1);
- b)** Provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1) would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

29.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- a)** display the EU emblem, and
- b)** include the following text: *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818123 (iAtlantic)".*

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must be prominent. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

29.5 Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

29.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43). Such a breach may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

1.5 Trusted Research Data Repositories

The research output generated during the lifetime of the iAtlantic project will be very diverse, including data, software and scientific articles from oceanographic parameters and disciplines ranging from physical oceanography, biogeochemistry, climate model outputs, visual surveys of biodiversity, biological rates and traits measurements, genetic and genomic analyses, socio-economic metrics, seafloor mapping, and spatial planning. This diversity requires an ambitious data management plan, building on existing open science resources (listed below) that are interoperable and trusted, while the activities are centrally coordinated by a data manager at the UniHB.

Selected trusted open science resources for archiving datasets generated by iAtlantic:

- PANGAEA, Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science (<http://www.pangaea.de>)
- EMODnet, the European Marine Observation and Data Network (<http://www.emodnet.eu/data-portfolio>)
- ENA, the European Nucleotides Archive (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>)NRF-SAEON, South African Environmental Observation Network Data archive (+win@saeon.ac.za)
- SEANOE (<http://en.data.ifremer.fr/Submit-Archive-data/SEANOE>)
- BODC PDL, British Oceanographic Data Centre 'Published Data Library' (<https://www.bodc.ac.uk/>)

Authors obliged by their institution to publish research data in alternative trustable resources, are permitted to do so with iAtlantic datasets. Conditions are the trustable resource is following the FAIR principles for data publication and authors inform the data manager (mnaumann@marum.de) at UniHB.

1.6 Open Research Data Compliance and related iAtlantic Tasks

Emphasis will additionally be placed on making the data available for creating integrated geospatial datasets and data products that will further increase the use of the datasets and uptake and impact for iAtlantic by wider stakeholders, including maritime industry. For example, EMODnet assembles open access datasets but also creates integrated maps to visualize data and to produce other data products, available through the EMODnet central portal, its 7 thematic portals are searchable in one place through the EMODnet data and data portfolio. Data will also be accessible via global data access portals like GEOSS. iAtlantic's data management responsibility will ultimately rest with UniHB, but is collaboratively managed with South Atlantic Partners NRF-SAEON and Centro de Hidrografia da Marinha (BNDO), reflecting the international profile of the project. This will be done in frequent dialogue with the EMODnet Secretariat (administered by iAtlantic partner Seascope Belgium) to ensure data and metadata are standardized to be INSPIRE³-compliant, ready for upload to the iAtlantic web-GIS platform (GEONODE), and long-term integration into the EMODnet open source data and data product services.

Following the guidelines of the ORD, there is no binding commitment of project partners to archive their data with the listed data repositories. However, we strongly encourage the project participants to ensure that iAtlantic data conforms to requirements set by the ORD. In addition, data archiving will be handled centrally by UniHB (PANGAEA), who will provide guidance and recommendation on data archiving prior to submission. The listed repositories are mature and sustainable infrastructures following common standards and formats, which will also enable the wider dissemination of the data through harvesting by global and thematic portals from these archives. Holding metadata records in PANGAEA for resources archived elsewhere will be at times necessary and appropriate workflows will be established.

In compliance with H2020's Open Research Data Pilot, the listed repositories ensure that **data sets are archived and preserved** using a **reference and name** (i.e. authors, year, title, DOI or accession number), a **description** (i.e. targeted use, geolocation, methods, link to related articles), and community **standards and metadata** (i.e. parameter semantics, formats, units, and use of ontologies and registries).

To ensure that relevant links between genetic and environmental information be maintained at the dataset level, the GFBio e. V. (<https://www.gfbio.org/>) brokering service will aid in the data submission in regards to genetic sequence data. Their strategy ensures that e.g. gene-based species lists from environmental samples at ENA are permanently referenced to environmental data at PANGAEA and vice versa, providing a forward looking and holistic approach to data management and actively supporting the FAIR archiving of data.

³ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

Unless authors request that data be embargoed (see iAtlantic's Open Science Policy below), data sets archived at ENA, PANGAEA, NRF-SAEON and EMODnet are published open access. Moreover, data sharing with EMODnet, as a long-term European marine observation and data sharing facility of the European Commission (DG MARE), ensures that iAtlantic is contributing to key European marine environmental policies e.g. Marine Knowledge 2020. iAtlantic data management will include standardization of data and metadata (Task 7.4) to be INSPIRE-compliant and ready for long-term distribution and dissemination also through EMODnet, to maximize the sharing and impact of iAtlantic data to the European services and European Union, as funders of the project. In addition, an All Atlantic Community Site on the GEOSS Portal (Tasks 7.5) will be produced, which aims to integrate data resources from across the Atlantic in a searchable metadata catalogue with direct data access provisions. The GEOSS Portal⁴ is a global initiative and will ensure a global reach of iAtlantic, addressing the widest possible number of users/stakeholders. The community page in the GEOSS Portal will serve as another source to find and retrieve Atlantic data and observation resources which are openly available. This development will take into account the need to be complementary and cross-reference the existing EMODnet Atlantic community pages, available on EMODnet's central portal.

A list of data and metadata expected from iAtlantic research activities is provided in Appendix I, based on previous EU projects that conducted similar studies, i.e. ATLAS, HERMES, HERMIONE and CoralFISH and with input from the iAtlantic WP leaders. A Table in Appendix II of the DMP lists the expected datasets and approximate data volumes for data management planning. The Data Management Plan of iAtlantic is coordinated by WP 7 and follows these objectives/tasks:

- a) Provide a plan and workflows for iAtlantic data handling and archiving according to the FAIR principles (data will be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable)
- b) Provide data handling and harvesting expertise in training opportunities
- c) Ensure wider and long-term data dissemination through EMODnet's data portals and resources for all Atlantic stakeholders, including those in the North West and South Atlantic, and through the European Atlas of the Seas
- d) Work on growing the international data community around Atlantic Ocean Observations through a thematic GEOSS Portal interface and EMODnet

⁴ <https://www.geoportal.org/>

The following task descriptions outline the work planned out in iAtlantic to achieve the data management objectives.

Task 7.1 Data Management Plan

This task comprises the creation of this document (DMP), which identifies and specifies what data will be open access and provides guidelines for its discovery, access, use, re-use and for its curation and preservation. The DMP is a dynamic document which will be altered to accommodate new data sources and newly established workflows. Considering the large quantity of data flowing into the project from other sources, this task will require a substantial effort from UniHB, but will also require active cooperation from all iAtlantic partners to provide the needed information. The DMP will follow the general EU guideline in regard to research data access: 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. The DMP also specifies metadata standards and emphasizes the necessity of allocating persistent identifiers for all generated data.

Task 7.2 Data submission and harmonisation

This task carries on for the entire duration of the project and covers the curation of (raw) data generated by the project, including providing guidance on dataset granularity and harmonization of data and metadata. Production and archiving of uniquely identifiable and re-usable datasets and making these data(sets) available to various open science resources (EMODnet, PANGAEA, OpenAIRE, Scholix, GEOSS) and projects (THOR, FREYA). UNIHB will support partners in preparing their data for submission to PANGAEA or coordinate submission to another suitable repository (e.g. for gene sequence data through GfBio). In this respect, PANGAEA will work to accommodate specific needs in respect to subsequent data analyses (aggregating files, establishing workflows etc.). All iAtlantic data producers will cooperate with PANGAEA and EMODnet to ensure that relevant geospatial data required by WP5, for marine spatial planning and management, are delivered in a timely manner and standardized for upload to the iAtlantic web-GIS platform (Task 5.2). EMODnet and PANGAEA will also cooperate to enable the timely data flow from PANGAEA to EMODnet as input for EMODnet where it will be acknowledged as iAtlantic data contributing to integrated datasets and data products for visualisation and download.

Task 7.4 Interfacing with Marine Observation Data Portals for wider dissemination

This task focuses on establishing or improving current links between the iAtlantic consortium and the marine observation and data communities with regards to data flow and dissemination of data products.

This will ensure that data and products (e.g. geospatial data layers, maps) generated by iAtlantic are made available via key marine observation and data sharing facilitates, in particular via EMODnet. The task includes:

- i) reviewing the harvesting protocols in place to ensure that data stored in PANGAEA are made available via EMODnet data portals;
- ii) facilitate the selection of relevant geospatial datasets collected by iAtlantic to produce map layers for the iAtlantic web-GIS (GEONODE), to assist the delivery of WP5 marine spatial planning and to visualize the iAtlantic data for project partners and wider stakeholders; and
- iii) to make them available via relevant ocean data portals and online map viewers (e.g. EMODnet, MARCO) for wider dissemination, including where relevant and possible to the European Atlas of the Seas, a communication tool of the European Commission (DG MARE).

Channelling these data resources via EMODnet to the global Atlantic community will directly contribute to DG MARE's EMODnet for global strategy. Once harvested by EMODnet, iAtlantic data will be available as part of integrated datasets and data products for viewing and download. Through the EMODnet web services, data and data products are also discoverable as remote web services by other data portals e.g. through machine-machine communication. The overarching strategy is to make iAtlantic data as **Findable** and **Accessible** as currently possible. This will increase the impact of the project output and contribute to the FAIR initiative.

Task 7.5 GEOSS All-Atlantic Community Portal

To establish a more global data dissemination platform for Atlantic data resources an All-Atlantic community site will be built in the GEOSS Portal. The aim is to draw together the international Atlantic observation community by strengthening and growing the network of actors in Atlantic Ocean observations. This will take into account the need to be complementary and cross-reference the existing EMODnet Atlantic community pages, available on EMODnet's central portal.

2. iAtlantic Data Policy

Timing and publication of research output

The iAtlantic Data Policy provides a clear workflow for safeguarding and sharing research outputs for reuse by researchers, industry stakeholders and policy makers. Research outputs include **preliminary (draft)** and **final versions** of data sets, and may include intermediate data products e.g. maps, articles, cruise summary reports, presentations, posters, code, and software. In compliance with Article 29 of the Grant Agreement, and following best practices described in the Data Management Plan, individuals who are involved in iAtlantic activities will:

- Register at ORCID (<http://orcid.org/>) and communicate their ORCID ID to the iAtlantic project office (i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk);
- Provide the iAtlantic Project Office (i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk) with a [ROR ID](#) for their hosting institution. To obtain a ROR ID please go to: <https://ror.org/> and apply the search function;
- Ensure that 30 days prior to submitting research output for publication (e.g. submitting a manuscript to a scientific journal), a **preliminary (draft) version** is sent to the iAtlantic project office (i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk) and Murray Roberts (murray.roberts@ed.ac.uk), indicating where it will be submitted. The draft can consist of the complete research output (e.g. full manuscript), or include at minimum the title, authors and abstract. The project office will make sure that the EC is properly acknowledged in the research output and will send the authors a contribution number. The draft will be placed on the password protected area of the EU-iAtlantic website and all iAtlantic partners will be informed by email by the Project Office. Comments about the draft research output should be sent directly to the authors and any concerns should be raised with the project coordinator. Unless issues have been raised during a period of 30 days, it is considered that all partners have read the research output and agree with its content;
- Provide the project data manager (mnaumann@uni-bremen.de) and the Project Office (i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk) with information regarding the publication status and persistent identifier(s) of the related datasets(s) at the time of announcing the new iAtlantic research publication.
- Ensure that a **preliminary version** of Cruise Summary Reports (CSRs) is submitted to PANGAEA no later than **3 months** after the cruise. CSRs should include a list of georeferenced sampling activities, measured parameters and contact details of principal investigators for each parameter;
- Ensure that **final versions** of Cruise Reports (CRs) are submitted to PANGAEA and deposited in open access at ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/iatlantic-project-collection>) no later than **6 months** after the cruise. CRs should include more detailed cruise information **in addition** to the CSR.

This includes, but is not limited to:

- Summary and itinerary
- Objectives
- Work at Sea
- Preliminary (expected) results
- Data management (use this document as a reference)
- Participating institutions*
- Cruise participants*
- Ship's crew*
- Station list

*include only personal information that can be made publicly available

- Ensure that the **final version** of all other research outputs (i.e. no datasets) is deposited at ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/iatlantic-project-collection>) as soon as possible and no later than three months after their production. Access to these research outputs can be restricted;
- Ensure that research outputs are made available preferably in gold open access (or a least green open access) as soon as possible and at the latest six months after dataset publication; **12 months** for publications in the social sciences and humanities; **24 months** in the case of unpublished data that are part of a research thesis;

Research Data submissions

- Ensure that data supporting any type of research output are deposited in a trusted archive (see DMP Section 1.5) and that research outputs and datasets cross-reference each other. Dataset publications receive a full reference (incl. DOI), which needs to be included in the reference list of the research publication. This is **in addition to** entries in the “Data Availability Section” that many journals nowadays offer.
- Ensure that research data, for which access is currently not in the public domain, is made available on request if required for iAtlantic project purposes. This should be done without undue delay, online and free of charge.
- Ensure that data collected during iAtlantic cruises (with the exception of experimental data) are submitted within **1 year** of completion of the cruise (data set publication), unless required by other iAtlantic partners at an earlier time. The dataset authors have the option to restrict access to their datasets for up to 3 years and, in exceptional circumstances, for longer time periods. This needs to be approved by the SC.
- Ensure that research data acquired from experimental setups are submitted within **1 year** of the end of the experiment. Data resulting from further sample processing (e.g. genetic analysis of

experimental samples) should be submitted as soon as a final dataset version is available and submitted referencing related datasets already published at an earlier time.

- Ensure where possible, that geospatial data published (DOI) in trusted repositories (PANGAEA, SAEON, SAENO, or other) are delivered as soon as possible to the web-GIS platform (GEONODE), enabling the production and visualization of iAtlantic geospatial data on the platform together with other open source geospatial data (e.g. data and maps already on EMODnet) to support the delivery of these products to iAtlantic WP5.

iAtlantic data sharing and dissemination principles

- The iAtlantic project strongly supports free, open, and immediate access to data and metadata produced by the project beneficiaries and is committed to working towards the realisation of this principle, taking into consideration ethical matters. This is in accordance with the Aarhus Convention on environmental data, the INSPIRE directive and the Directive 2003/4/EC (on public access to environmental information).
- All data, metadata or data services generated during the project will be made available to an agreed standard and in an agreed format through designated data repositories and coordinated through PANGAEA. Appropriate domain specific ontologies and controlled dictionaries such as the BODC vocabularies (also used in SEADATANET) should be used within iAtlantic metadata descriptions and are referenced in Appendix I.
- Data provision / deposition is under the responsibility of data providers.
- Free and open access without any restrictions shall be granted to all data and metadata.
- The iAtlantic consortium recognises that under exceptional circumstances (as pertains to e.g. commercial data provided to consortium members), data access may be restricted for a limited period of time or indefinitely, if circumstances require. This must be agreed with the project steering committee in advance.
- All data, data products and metadata derived from the iAtlantic project must be appropriately attributed in any publications to the members responsible for their acquisition
- Data and associated metadata will be subject to long-term archiving, typically at the selected repositories listed in chapter 6 of the iAtlantic Data Management Plan (D7.1, vers. 1)
- Unless stewardship of data is explicitly transferred, the general responsibility for data sets that have searchable metadata records in PANGAEA, while the data is actually archived elsewhere, remains entirely with the hosting institution. Hosting repositories are then required to inform PANGAEA (and the GEOSS Portal) about changes applied to the embedded dataset links.

iAtlantic data requirements

- Data will be deposited either:
 - a. in one of the data repositories listed in chapter 1.5 of the DMP, or
 - b. an appropriate data centre providing long-term archiving services following FAIR data publication principles; authors are required to inform the project data manager (mnaumann@marum.de) at UniHB.
- Access to all data will be made simply and easily through the iAtlantic Catalogue of Resources (D7.3), to be made available on the iAtlantic project website and through the GEOSS community page and EMODnet Atlantic community page.

For any questions or assistance regarding the dissemination and exploitation of:

- **preliminary (draft) and final versions** of your research outputs, please contact the iAtlantic Project Office, (i-atlantic@ed.ac.uk)
- **research data generated in iAtlantic** or questions regarding data submission and publication, please contact Malik Naumann (mnaumann@marum.de)
- **for questions regarding functionality and use of the iAtlantic GeoNode web-platform**, please contact Tim Collart (tim.collart@seascapebelgium.be) or Kate Larkin (kate.larkin@seascapebelgium.be)
- **final versions of public outreach materials**, please contact Vikki Gunn (vikki.gunn@seascapeconsultants.co.uk), and consult the Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach Plan (DEOP) on the “Member’s area” of iAtlantic website.

3. Appendix I – Parameters expected from iAtlantic research activities

The following table was compiled from data sets published from three previous European projects that were similar in scope to iAtlantic, i.e. ATLAS, HERMES, HERMIONE and CoralFISH. We therefore expect that the parameters listed in this table will either be measured during field and experimental campaigns organised by or in collaboration with iAtlantic partners, or re-used from already published data sets.

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
amount concentration of biological entity per unit mass of environmental entity	Bacteria, abundance per unit sediment mass	10 ⁶ #/g
amount concentration of biological entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Prokaryotes, abundance as single cells; Bacteria, abundance	10 ⁹ #/cm ³
amount concentration of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Acid volatile sulphides; Chromium reducible sulphides; Iron ascorbic acid extraction; Iron dithionite extraction; Ammonium; Carbon, inorganic, dissolved; Carbon, organic, dissolved; Iron, total, dissolved; Nitrate; Nitrite; Nitrogen, total dissolved; Oxygen; Phosphate; Silicate; Sulfite; Sulphide; Thiosulphate; Concentration; Heptasulphide; Hexasulphide; Iron 2+; Pentasulphide; Polythionate; Tetrasulphide; Trisulphide; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water cyanolysis; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water ZnCl ₂ extraction; Sulphur, elemental; Alkalinity, total; Chloride; Sulphate; Phospholipids; Adenylates, total	μmol/cm ³ ; μmol/l; μmol/ml; mmol(eq)/l; mmol/l; nmol/ml; pmol/cm ³
amount rate of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	Methane flux; Oxygen flux, sediment oxygen demand; Methane, oxidation rate, anaerobic	mmol/m ² /day
amount rate of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Esterase activity per sediment volume	nmol/ml/h
mass concentration of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	Carbon, organic, particulate per area, fraction; Carbon, total particulate; Carbon, total particulate, fraction; Nitrogen, organic, particulate; Nitrogen, organic, particulate, fraction; Carbon, organic, particulate per area; Particle concentration, resuspendable; Marine litter, mass per area	g/m ² ; kg/km ²

<p>mass concentration of chemical entity per unit mass of environmental entity</p>	<p>Amino acid, hydrolysable per unit sediment mass; Amino acids per unit sediment mass; Carbohydrates, acid soluble; Carbohydrates, NaOH soluble; Carbohydrates, total; Lipids, total; Proteins, total; Acenaphthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthylene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthylene, per unit mass organic carbon; alpha-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; alpha-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)pyrene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)pyrene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(b)fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(b)fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(g,h,i)perylene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(g,h,i)perylene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(k)fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(k)fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Chrysene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Chrysene, per unit mass organic carbon; Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluorene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluorene, per unit mass organic carbon; gamma-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; gamma-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Hexachlorobenzene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Hexachlorobenzene, per unit mass organic carbon; Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Indeno (1,2,3-cd)pyrene, per unit mass organic carbon; Naphthalene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Naphthalene, per unit mass organic carbon; ortho,para-Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane, fraction, per unit mass organic C;</p>	<p>µg/g; mg/kg; ng/kg</p>
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mass concentration of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Chloroplastic pigment equivalents per area; Chloroplastic pigment equivalents per volume; Chlorophyll a; Chlorophyll pigment equivalents; Phaeopigments; Carbon, organic, total per volume; Density, sigma, in situ; Density, sigma2000; Density, sigma-theta (0); Density, mass density; Protein, readily soluble per sediment volume	$\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$; $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$; kg/m^3 ; mg/cm^3
mass concentration of chemical entity; biological entity per unit area of environmental entity	Bacteria, biomass as carbon; Benthos, biomass as carbon; Biomass as carbon; Copepoda, biomass as carbon; Meiofauna, biomass as carbon; Nematoda, biomass as carbon; Polychaeta, biomass as carbon	$\mu\text{g}/10\text{ cm}^2$; mg/m^2
mass of biological entity	Amblyraja radiata, mass; Anarhichas denticulatus, mass; Anarhichas lupus, mass; Brosme brosme, mass; Chimaera monstrosa, mass; Etmopterus spinax, mass; Gadus morhua, mass; Galeus melastomus, mass; Gorgonacea, mass; Lithodes maja, mass; Lophelia pertusa, mass; Melanogrammus aeglefinus, mass; Molva molva, mass; Pollachius virens, mass; Porifera, mass; Rajella fyllae, mass; Sebastes norvegicus, mass	kg
mass rate of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	24-Ethylcholest-5-en-3beta-ol flux; 24-Methylcholest-5-en-3beta-ol flux; 24-Methylcholesta-5,22E-dien-3beta-ol flux; all-cis-4,7,10,13,16,19-Docosahexaenoic acid flux; all-cis-5,8,11,14,17-Icosapentaenoic acid flux; all-cis-6,9,12,15-Octadecatetraenoic acid flux; Cholesta-5-en-3beta-ol flux; cis-11-Hexadecenoic acid flux; cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid flux; Lipids flux; Biogenic flux; Biopolymeric carbon flux; Calcium carbonate flux; Carbohydrate flux; Carbon, inorganic, particulate flux per day; Carbon, organic, particulate flux per day; Flux of total mass; Lithogenic flux per day; Nitrogen, organic, particulate flux per day; Nitrogen, particulate flux; Opal flux; Organic matter flux; Protein total flux; Silica, particulate flux per day; Silicon, particulate flux; Total mass flux per day	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$; $\text{mg}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$
mass rate of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Sulphate reduction rate; Methane, oxidation rate	$\text{nmol}/\text{cm}^3/\text{day}$
mass rate of chemical entity; biological entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Bacterial biomass production of carbon	$\text{ng}/\text{l}/\text{h}$

metadata	Buildup; Taxa analyzed; Replicates; Seismic line; Mesh size; Sample surface; Time, incubation; Duration, number of days; Signal strength; Pressure, water; Current direction; Current meter, pitch; Current meter, roll; Current meter, tilt; Course; Direction; Duration; File size; Depth, bottom/max; Depth, top/min; DEPTH, sediment/rock; DEPTH, water; Depth, bathymetric; Height above sea floor/altitude; Recovery; Taxon/taxa; Position; Description; Experimental treatment; Area/locality; Comment; Date/time end; Date/time start; Device type; Event; File name; Gear; Latitude 2; Longitude 2; Parameter; Reference of data; Reference/source; Sample code/label; Sample comment; Split; DATE/TIME; LATITUDE; LONGITUDE; ORDINAL NUMBER; Sorting; Species; Core; File format; Log info; Number; Profile; Sample ID; Sample, optional label/labor no; Shoot point; Site; Treatment; Type; Uniform resource locator/link to file; Uniform resource locator/link to graphic; Uniform resource locator/link to image; Uniform resource locator/link to metadata file; Uniform resource locator/link to movie; Uniform resource locator/link to raw data file; Uniform resource locator/link to sgy data file; Uniform resource locator/link to thumbnail; Cruise/expedition; Depth, bathymetric, maximum; Depth, bathymetric, minimum; ELEVATION; Feature; Filter; Hooks; Identification; Legibility; Location; Method comment; Seastate label; Section; Species code; Status	
non-parametric quality of biological entity	Sex; Stage; Morphology	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity	Coral Status; Food; Habitat; Substrate type; Morphology	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity per unit biological entity	Coral; Amblyraja radiata; Anarhichas denticulatus; Anarhichas lupus; Brosme brosme; Chimaera monstrosa; Clupea harengus abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; Etmopterus spinax; Fish; Gadus morhua; Gorgonacea; Lithodes maja; Lophelia pertusa; Melanogrammus aeglefinus; Molva molva; Pollachius virens; Rajella fyllae; Sebastes norvegicus; Sponge	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity per unit anthropogenic entity	Marine litter, clinker; Marine litter, fabric; Marine litter, fishing net; Marine litter, glass; Marine litter, hard plastic; Marine litter, long line; Marine litter, metal; Marine litter, oil drum; Marine litter, soft plastic	

parametric quality of environmental entity	Food index; Porosity; Species richness; Dauwe index; Diversity; Equitability; Shannon index of diversity	
parametric quality of environmental entity per unit biological entity	Nematoda, trophic diversity; Mesopelagic fish abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; Micromesistius poutassou abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; Plankton abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; Pollachius virens abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient	
parametric quality of physical entity	Temperature, in rock/sediment; Temperature, water; Temperature, water, potential; Fluorescence; Turbidity; Echo backscatter; Turbidity (Formazin Turbidity Unit); Conductivity; Oxidation reduction (RedOx) potential; pH; Salinity; Dissolved oxygen; Attenuation, optical beam transmission; Humidity, relative; Pressure, atmospheric; Radiation, photosynthetically active; Temperature, air; Wind direction	degC; arbitrary units; dB; mS/cm; mV; mg/ L; ml/L
ratio of biological entity per unit biological entity	Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1 archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1-350 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a-647 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a,b; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2c; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3 archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3-1249 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Archaea, Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1; Archaea, GEG; Archaea, GoM Arc I; Archaea, MBG-B; Archaea, MBG-D; Archaea, targeted with ARCH915 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Methanomicrobiales; Methanosaeta related Methanosarcinales; Methanosarcinales, unaffiliated; Acidobacteria; Acrobacter spp., targeted with ARC94 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Actinobacteria; Alphaproteobacteria; Bacteria; Bacteria, JS1; Bacteria, OP11; Bacteria, OP8; Bacteria, tagged with EUB338(I-III) oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Bacteria, TG1; Bacteria, unaffiliated; Bacteria, WS2; Bacteria, WS3; Bacteroidetes; Betaproteobacteria; Chlorobi; Chloroflexi; Deferribacteres; Delta-Proteobacteria; Desulfusarcina/Desulfococcus, targeted with DSS658 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Epsilonproteobacteria; Firmicutes; Fusobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Planctomycetes; Spirochaetes; Meiofauna; Foraminifera, benthic hyaline; Adelosina spp.; Ammolagena clavata; Ammonia beccarii; Amphicoryna scalaris; Angulogerina angulosa; Articulina tubulosa; Asterigerinata mamilla; Astrononion stelligerum; Bigenerina nodosaria; Biloculinella depressa; Biloculinella inflata; Biloculinella labiata; Bolivina psudoplicata;	

Bolivina pseudopunctata; Brizalina alata; Brizalina albatrossi; Brizalina dilatata; Brizalina subaenariensis; Bulimina aculeata; Bulimina costata; Bulimina elongata; Bulimina marginata; Bulimina striata mexicana; Cassidulina laevigata; Cassidulina oblonga; Cassidulinoides bradyi; Chilostomella oolina; Cibicides lobatulus; Cibicides spp.; Cibicidoides pachyderma; Cibicidoides spp.; Cornuspira involvens; Dentalina albatrossi; Dentalina spp.; Discammina compressa; Discanomalina semipunctata; Discorbinella bertheloti; Discorbis spp.; Elphidium spp.; Epistominella rugosa; Fissurina spp.; Fursenkoina cf. acuta; Fursenkoina mexicana; Gavelinopsis praegeri; Glandulina spp.; Globobulimina affinis; Globobulimina pseudospinescens; Globobulimina spp.; Glomospira charoides; Guttulina cf. communis; Gyroidinoides neosoldanii; Gyroidinoides orbicularis; Gyroidinoides umbonatus; Haynesina spp.; High oxygen indicators; Hoeglundina elegans; Hyaline balthica; Laevidentalina flexuosa; Lagenella spp.; Lenticulina calcar; Lenticulina cultrata; Lenticulina orbicularis; Lenticulina spp.; Low oxygen indicators; Marginulina spp.; Marginulinopsis spp.; Melonis barleeanus; Miliolinella spp.; Miliolinella subrotunda; Neoconorbina terquemi; Neolenticulina peregrina; Nonion asterizans; Nonion depressulum; Nonionella turgida; Nummoloculina contraria; Oolina spp.; Paracassidulina minuta; Patellina corrugata; Placopsilina sp.; Planorbulina mediterraneensis; Planulina ariminensis; Polymorphina spp.; Pseudoclavulina crustata; Pseudotriloculina laevigata; Pseudotriloculina oblonga; Pullenia bulloides; Pullenia salisburyi; Pullenia subcarinata; Pyrgo cf. murrhina; Pyrgo comata; Pyrgo elongata; Pyrgo inornata; Pyrgo spp.; Pyrgoella sphaera; Quinqueloculina laevigata; Quinqueloculina milletti; Quinqueloculina padana; Quinqueloculina seminula; Quinqueloculina spp.; Quinqueloculina venusta; Quinqueloculina viennensis; Repmanina charoides; Reussella spinulosa; Rhabdammina sp.; Robertinoides translucens; Rosalina bradyi; Rosalina spp.; Rotamorphina involuta; Sigmoidina costata; Sigmoidina sigmoidea; Sigmoidinita tenuis; Sigmoidinopsis schlumbergeri; Siphonaperta aspera; Siphonina reticulata; Siphonotextularia heterostoma; Sphaeroidina bulloides; Spiroloculina sp.; Spiroplectinella sagittula; Textularia agglutinans; Textularia pala; Triloculina spp.; Triloculina tricarinata; Uvigerina mediterranea; Uvigerina peregrina; Uvigerina proboscidea; Valvulinaria bradyana

ratio of chemical entity per unit chemical entity	Alanine; alpha-aminobutyric acid; Arginine; Asparagine; beta-Alanine; gamma-Aminobutyric acid; Glutamine; Glycine; Histidine; Isoleucine; Leucine; Lysine; Methionine; Ornithine; Phenylalanine; Serine; Threonine; Tyrosine; Valine; Nitrogen, organic, fraction; Oxygen, saturation; Methane; Organic matter; Ethane; n-Butane; Propane; Isobutane; Hydrate; Water content of wet mass; Aluminium; Calcium; Calcium carbonate; Carbon, inorganic, total; Carbon, organic, fraction; Carbon, organic, particulate; Carbon, organic, total; Carbon, total; Iron; Magnesium; Nitrogen, organic; Nitrogen, total; Opal, biogenic silica; Silicon; Sulphur, total; Lithogenic material; Volcanic glass, acidic; delta 15N; delta 15N, particulate organic nitrogen; delta 234 Uranium; Acid volatile sulphides isotopes; Chromium reducible sulphides isotopes; delta 13C; delta 13C, adjusted/corrected; delta 13C, organic carbon; delta 13C, particulate organic carbon; C1/C2 hydrocarbon ratio; C1/C2+ hydrocarbon ratio; C1/C3 hydrocarbon ratio; Lead 206/Lead 207; Lead 208/Lead 206 ratio; Neodymium 143/Neodymium 144; Strontium 87/Strontium 86 ratio; epsilon-Neodymium (0); Thorium 230/Thorium 232 ratio; Thorium 230/Uranium 234 ratio; Uranium 234/Uranium 238 activity ratio; Uranium 238/Thorium 232 ratio; Calcium/(Calcium+Iron) ratio; Carbon/Nitrogen ratio; Carbon/Sulphur ratio; Nitrogen/Carbon ratio	
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<p>unit concentration of biological entity per unit area of environmental entity</p>	<p>Eumeiofauna; Meiofauna, abundance; Pseudomeiofauna; Abundance per area; Benthos, other; Copepoda indeterminata; Meiofauna, abundance of foraminifera; Meiofauna, abundance of harpacticoida; Meiofauna, abundance of metazoa; Cladocera; Foraminifera, benthic; Lysianassidae; Scaphopoda; Anomonema; Chitwoodia; Comesomoides; Cricolaimus; Cylicolaimus; Demonema; Desmocolex; Diplolaimelloides; Echinodesmodora; Endeolophos; Eubostrichus; Eudiplogaster; Gairleanema; Gomphionchus; Gonionchus; Kraspedonema; Leptonemella; Metadasyneoides; Monoposthia; Morlaixia; Odontophoroides; Omicronema; Parachromadorita; Paradesmodora; Parallelocoilas; Paranticoma; Perspiria; Polysigma; Pontonema; Prochromadora; Psammonema; Pseudocella; Steineridora; Trichotheristus; Valvaelaimus; Cirratulidae; Maldanidae; Paramphinome sp.; Spionidae; Acari; Amphimonhystrella bullacauda; Antarcticconema; Asellota; Bathyepsilonema; Calanoidea; Cheironchus; Ciliata; Comesoma; Cyatholaimus; Deontolaimus; Desmodora pilosa; Desmodoroidea; Desmolorenzenia; Desmotricoma; Dorylaimopsis; Ethmolaimidae; Goniadidae; Greeffiellinae; Greeffiellopsis; Halanonchus; Hesionidae; Ixonema; Karkinochromadora; Lacydoniidae; Lumbrineridae; Metacomesea; Metacycolaimus; Monhysterina; Nannolaimoides; Nephtyidae; Nicascolaimus; Notochaetosoma; Nyctonema; Opheliidae; Ophiuroidea; Pandolaimus; Paraethmolaimus; Paraonidae; Parapinnanema; Pareudesmoscolex; Phoxocephalidae; Phyllodocidae; Pilargidae; Prochaetosoma; Pseudolella; Quadricoma; Sabatieria bitumen; Sabatieria conicauda; Sabatieria demani; Sabatieria lawsi; Sabatieria ornata; Sabatieria propisina; Sabatieria punctata; Sabatieria stekhoveni; Sabatieria vasicola; Sipuncula; Synonchium; Tanaoidea; Tarvaia; Tetrapturus; Thoracostomopsis; Amphinomidae; Capitellidae; Glyceridae; Terebellidae; Virus; Carrier crab; Copepoda; Crab; Edible crab; Galeus melastomus; Gastrotricha; Kinorhyncha; Nematoda genus sp.; Number of clones; Number of individuals; Phylotype number; Shrimps; Small grenadier; Spinder crab; Squat lobster; Swimmer crab; Foraminifera, benthic agglutinated; Foraminifera, benthic agglutinated indeterminata; Foraminifera, benthic calcareous; Foraminifera, benthic perforates indeterminata; Foraminifera, chitineous; Insects, total counts; Ostracoda; Ameira; Ameirinae; Ameiropsis; Amphiascoidea; Amphiascus; Archesola; Argestes; Argestidae; Atergopedia; Bathycamptus; Bodinia; Bradya; Bradyellopsis; Canthocamptidae; Cletodes; Cyclopoida; Cyldrionannopus; Diarthrodella; Dizahavia; Ectinosoma; Ectinosomatidae; Enhydrosoma; Eurycletodes; Filexilia; Fultonia; Halectinosoma; Halophytophilus; Haloschizopera; Hastigerella; Heterolaophonte; Idomene; Idyanthe; Idyanthidae; Idyella; Klieosoma; Kliopsyllus; Laophonte; Laophontodes; Leptomesochra; Leptopsyllus; Lineosoma; Lobopleura; Malacopsyllus; Marsteinia; Mesochra; Mesocletodes; Metahuntemannia; Microsetella; Misophrioida; Nematovorax; Neobryidae; Novocriniidae; Parameiropsis; Parameseochra; Parameseochridae;</p>	<p>#: #/10 cm²; #/m²</p>
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Parapseudoleptomesochra; Peltobradya; Perissocope; Poecilostomatoida; Pseudameira;
 Pseudobradya; Pseudomesochra; Pseudotachidiinae; Rhyncholagena; Rhynchothalestris;
 Robertgurneya; Sagamiella; Sarsameira; Scottopsyllus; Sigmatidium; Siphonostomatoida;
 Stenocopia; Talpina; Tegastes; Tetragonicepsidae ; Xylora; Zosime; Dendrophyllia cornigera;
 Desmophylum; Lophelia; Madrepora oculata; Centrophorus squamosus; Helicolenus dactylopterus
 dactylopterus; Hexanchus griseus; Lepidion eques; Lopheous piscatorious; Mora moro; Phycis
 blennoides; Synaphobranchus kaupi; Dendrophyllia; Madrepora; Actinonema; Adoncholaimus;
 Aegialoalaimidae; Amphimonhystera; Anticyathus; Aponema; Araeolaimus; Ascolaimus;
 Astomonema; Bathynox; Benthimermithidae; Bodonema; Bolbolaimus; Calligyru; Catanema;
 Cephalanticoma; Ceramonema; Chaetonema; Choanolaimus; Chromadorella; Chromadoridae;
 Cobbia; Comesa; Comesomatidae; Coninckia; Cyatholaimidae; Dasynemoides; Desmodorella;
 Desmodoridae; Didelta; Diodontolaimus; Diplolaimella; Diplopeltidae; Diplopeltis; Disconema;
 Dolicholaimus; Doliolaimus; Draconema; Elzalia; Enchelidiidae; Enoplineae; Enoploides; Enoplus;
 Epacanthion; Euchromadora; Eurystomina; Filoncholaimus; Gammanema; Glochinema;
 Gnomoxyala; Graphonema; Greeffiella; Halichoanolaimus; Haliplectus; Halomonhystera;
 Hapalomus; Hopperia; Hypodontolaimus; Intasia; Laimella; Latronema; Leptosomatium;
 Linhomoeidae; Linhomoeus; Litinium; Longicyatholaimus; Megadesmolaimus; Mesacanthion;
 Mesacanthoides; Metachromadora; Metacyatholaimus; Metadasynemella; Metaparoncholaimus;
 Metasphaerolaimus; Metoncholaimus; Micoletzkyia; Microlaimidae; Minolaimus; Monhystera;
 Monhysteridae; Nannolaimus; Nemanema; Neochromadora; Neotonchus; Noffsingeria;
 Odontanticoma; Odontophora; Oncholaimellus; Oncholaimidae; Oncholaimus; Paracomesoma;
 Paralongicyatholaimus; Paramesonchium; Paramicrolaimus; Paramonhystera; Pararaeolaimus;
 Parasphaerolaimus; Parastomonema; Paratricoma; Pareurystomina; Parodontophora; Phanoderma;
 Phanodermatidae; Phanodermopsis; Pierrickia; Platycoma; Platycomopsis; Praeacanthonchus;
 Promonhystera; Prooncholaimus; Prototricoma; Pseudonchus; Pterygonema; Ptycholaimellus;
 Rhynchonema; Richtersia; Setoplectus; Setosabatieria; Siphonolaimus; Sphaerolaimidae;
 Spilophorella; Spinodesmoscolex; Spirobolbolaimus; Steineria; Stephanolaimus; Stylotheristus;
 Symplocostoma; Synodontium; Synonchiella; Synonchus; Thalassironus; Trefusia; Trefusialaimus;
 Tripyloides; Trissonchulus; Trochamus; Xennella; Xyala; Acantholaimus; Acanthonchus;
 Aegialoalaimus; Alaimella; Ammotheristus; Amphimonhystrella; Amphipoda; Anoplostoma;
 Anticoma; Antomicron; Aplacophora; Atrochromadora; Axonolaimus; Bathyeurystomina; Belbolla;
 Bivalvia; Calanoida; Calomicrolaimus; Calyptronema; Camacolaimus; Campylaimus; Cervonema;
 Chromadora; Chromadorina; Chromadorita; Chromaspirina; Cnidaria; Crenopharynx;

	<p>Cricohalalaimus; Cumacea; Cyartonema; Dagda; Daptonema; Desmodora; Desmolaimus; Desmoscolecida; Desmoscolex; Dichromadora; Diplopeltoides; Diplopeltula; Draconematidae; Echinodermata; Eleutherolaimus; Enoplolaimus; Epsilonema; Ethmolaimus; Eumorpholaimus; Fenestrolaimus; Filitonchus; Gerlachius; Gnathostomulida; Halacarida; Halalaimus; Holothuroidea; Hydrozoa; Indeterminata; Innocuonema; Intoshia; Isopoda; Ledovitia; Leptolaimoides; Leptolaimus; Linhystera; Loricifera; Manganonema; Marylynnia; Metadesmolaimus; Metepsilonema; Meyersia; Microlaimus; Molgolaimus; Monhystrella; Nauplii; Nematoda; Oligochaeta; Oxyonchus; Oxystomina; Paracanthonchus; Paracyatholaimoides; Paracyatholaimus; Paralinhomoeus; Paramesacanthion; Paramonohystera; Polychaeta; Pomponema; Porifera; Priapulida; Procamacolaimus; Prochromadorella; Pselionema; Pseudochromadora; Retrotheristus; Rhabdocoma; Rhabdodemia; Rhips; Rotifera; Sabatieria; Sipunculida; Southerniella; Sphaerolaimus; Spiliphera; Spirinia; Stygodesmodora; Subsphaerolaimus; Syncarida; Synonema; Syringolaimus; Tanaidacea; Tantulocarida; Tardigrada; Terschellingia; Thalassoalaimus; Thalassomonhystera; Theristus; Tricoma; Trileptium; Turbellaria; Vasostoma; Viscosia; Wieseria; Xyalidae; Metalinhomoeus; Adercotryma sp.; Ammodiscus sp.; Bolivina sp.; Buliminella sp.; Discorbinellidae indeterminata; Epistominella sp.; Fissurina sp.; Ioannella sp.; Lagenella sp.; Lagenammia sp.; Nodellum sp.; Oolina sp.; Reophax sp.; Triloculina sp.; Gastropoda; Harpacticoida</p>	
volume of biological entity	Bacteria, cell biovolume; Bacteria, heterotrophic, cell biovolume	μm ³
Sedimentary proxy data	<p>Grain-size distributions</p> <p>Stable isotopes</p> <p>Foraminifera accumulation rates</p> <p>Cold-water coral ages (U/Th)</p> <p>Foraminifera ages (14C)</p>	<p>Vol.-%</p> <p>‰ PDB</p> <p>ind cm-3 kyr-1</p> <p>kyr BP</p> <p>cal. kyr BP</p>

4. APPENDIX II - Dataset list with anticipated data volumes

iAtlantic WP	List of planned data acquisitions	iAtlantic Partner	Approx. data volumes anticipated
WP2, WP5	Benthic assemblage data	UFES Brazil Angelo Bernardino, angelo.bernardino@ufes.br IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas Cova.orejas@ieo.es	2 TB
WP2, WP5	Benthic and benthopelagic habitats description and community structure	UNIVALI Angel Perez Angel.perez@univali.br IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas Cova.orejas@ieo.es	1 GB 2 TB
WP3	Historical fishing data in open ocean off Brazil	UNIVALI Angel Perez Angel.perez@univali.br	250 MB
WP3	Sedimentary proxy data	UniHB Dierk Hebbeln dhebbeln@marum.de	1MB
WP2, WP4, WP5	coral species identification, distribution, description	UFSC Brazil Alberto Lindner, alberto.lindner@ufsc.br IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas Cova.orejas@ieo.es	100GB 2 TB
WP2, WP5	Multibeam bathymetry	AWI Boris Dorschel boris.dorschel@awi.de IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas cova.orejas@ieo.es IEO, Spain Jesús Rivera Jesus.rivera@ieo.es	10GB 100GB 250GB

WP1, WP3	High-resolution ocean model data (VIKING, INALT)	GEOMAR datamanagement@geomar.de	200GB
WP2, WP5	Bathymetry with ship multibeam	GEOMAR Anne-Cathrin Wölfl awoelfl@geomar.de IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas cova.orejas@ieo.es IEO, Spain Jesús Rivera Jesus.rivera@ieo.es UCC, Ireland Aaron Lim aaron.lim@ucc.ie, Andy Wheeler a.wheeler@ucc.ie	100GB 250GB
WP2, WP5	Benthic community data (species / abundance matrices)	NERC Daniel Jones dj1@noc.ac.uk IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas Cova.orejas@ieo.es	2 TB
WP3	Zooplankton composition and abundance from Multinet Hauls (day/night) at CVOO time series station	GEOMAR hhauss@geomar.de	uncertain
WP3	Particle/zooplankton profiles from Underwater Vision Profiler at CVOO time series station	GEOMAR hhauss@geomar.de	uncertain
WP3	ADCP backscatter and current velocities at CVOO time series station	GEOMAR hhauss@geomar.de	uncertain
WP3	CTD profiles at CVOO time series station	GEOMAR bfiedler@geomar.de	uncertain
WP2	Video-based pelagic macroplankton and nekton abundance	GEOMAR hhoving@geomar.de hhauss@geomar.de	uncertain
WP2, WP5	Geospatial data Oceanographic data	IEO, Spain Jesús Rivera jesus.rivera@ieo.es	60GB
WP2	Occurrence/Density / abundance Benthic organisms	IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas cova.orejas@ieo.es	2 TB

WP4	Ecophysiological data	IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas cova.orejas@ieo.es	1GB
WP2	Local bathymetry (Lampaul canyon)	Ifremer J. Tourolle (julie.tourolle@ifremer.fr)	uncertain
WP2	Habitat map (Lampaul canyon)	Ifremer J. Tourolle julie.tourolle@ifremer.fr T. Bajorouk touria.bajorouk@ifremer.fr	uncertain
WP2, WP5	Biodiversity	Ifremer L. Michel Loic.Michel@ifremer.fr IEO, Spain Covadonga Orejas Cova.orejas@ieo.es	2TB
WP3	Stable isotope ratios	Ifremer L. Michel Loic.Michel@ifremer.fr	uncertain
WP2	Time-series of temperature, oxygen and iron concentrations (Lucky Strike vent field)	Ifremer M. Matabos Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr	uncertain
WP2	2D/3D mosaic of the Lucky Strike vent field: habitat map, faunal distribution	Ifremer M. Matabos Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr	uncertain
WP2	Time-series of video data (Lucky Strike vent field)	Ifremer M. Matabos Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr	uncertain
WP1	All iAtlantic SW Atlantic mooring data (1 mooring including multilevel T,S, (probably) O2 and current velocity data)	SHN Maria Paz Chidichimo mpchidichimo@hidro.gov.ar DEA – Oceans and Coasts Tarron.Lamont@gmail.com UCT – Oceanography Isabelle.Ansorge@uct.ac.za	uncertain
WP1	In situ observations of oxygen concentration	SAMS Stuart.cunningham@sams.ac.uk DEA – Oceans and Coasts Tarron.Lamont@gmail.com	5MB
WP2	Benthic and planktic assemblage and	UCL	uncertain

	abundance data	David Thornalley d.thornalley@ucl.ac.uk	
WP2	Geochemical data	UCL David Thornalley d.thornalley@ucl.ac.uk	uncertain
WP2	Paleoceanographic reconstructions from sediment cores	UCL David Thornalley d.thornalley@ucl.ac.uk	uncertain
WP2	Compilations of literature data	UCL David Thornalley d.thornalley@ucl.ac.uk	uncertain
WP1	Pilot eDNA data	UCL David Thornalley d.thornalley@ucl.ac.uk	uncertain
WP3	GIS-layer - Colour-coded polygons for each large marine region (12 in total) on “Likelihood that future oceanographic changes will alter regional ecosystem”	UEDIN Lea-Anne Henry l.henry@ed.ac.uk	uncertain
WP2	DNA/RNA sequence data	NOC Julie Robidart, j.robidart@noc.ac.uk	uncertain
WP2	Environmental data	UCC, Ireland Aaron Lim aaron.lim@ucc.ie Andy Wheeler a.wheeler@ucc.ie	uncertain
WP3	Zooplankton, groundfish, squid data from Scotian Slope	DFO, Canada Trevor Kenchington Trevor.Kenchington@dfo-mpo.gc.ca Ellen Kenchington Ellen.Kenchington@dfo-mpo.gc.ca UEDIN, UK Lea-Anne Henry l.henry@ed.ac.uk	uncertain
WP3	Humpback whale data from Sargasso Sea	Whales Bermuda, USA Andrew Stevenson spout@logic.bm UEDIN, UK Lea-Anne Henry l.henry@ed.ac.uk	uncertain
WP3	BATS data from Sargasso Sea	BIOS, Nicholas Bates	uncertain

		UEDIN, UK Lea-Anne Henry l.henry@ed.ac.uk	
WP3	Humpback whales, zooplankton, pelagic and groundfish data	MFRI, Stefán Ragnarsson Stefan.ragnarsson@hafogvatn.is	uncertain

5. Document Information

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Project website	www.iatlantic.eu		

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	X	CO Confidential restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement		
		CI Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC		

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